

Tuning the magnon transport properties of $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ with a cobalt phthalocyanine molecular layer

*Peisen Yuan¹, Sara Catalano¹, Witold Skowronski^{1, 2}, Roger Llopis¹, F òix Casanova^{1, 3}
and Luis E Hueso,^{*1, 3}*

¹CIC nanoGUNE BRTA, 20018 Donostia–San Sebastian, Spain

²AGH University of Krakow, Institute of Electronics, 30-059 Krak ów, Poland

³IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48009 Bilbao, Spain

Keywords: magnon transport, interfacial hybridization, magnetic insulator, organic molecule

ABSTRACT

Transporting spin information using magnon currents in magnetic insulators has garnered considerable interest as a means to advance information technology. A material's magnon transport properties can be tuned indirectly by modifying the magnetic properties, on which the former heavily depend. Molecular functionalization, in which organic molecules form a hybrid interface with a substrate material, has been shown to be a promising approach to modify the magnetic properties of metallic materials. In this work, we go beyond metals and demonstrate that the interfacial interaction between the organic molecule cobalt phthalocyanine (CoPc) and the magnetic insulator $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YIG) modifies the magnetic properties of YIG, thereby allowing us to tune the transport properties of magnon currents in this magnetic insulator. Comparing a device with a YIG/CoPc interface to a simple YIG device, we find that the functionalized device exhibits larger amplitudes of nonlocal signals for both electrically and thermally excited magnon currents. Through the measurement of field-dependent nonlocal magnon signals and ferromagnetic resonance (FMR) in the YIG/CoPc device, we observe that the interfacial effect changes the magnetic anisotropy of YIG, resulting in a larger saturation field. Moreover, the device with the CoPc overlayer exhibits a larger electrically excited magnon diffusion length at low temperature due to the reduced Gilbert damping constant, as verified by FMR measurements. Our findings give us insight into the potential use of molecular functionalization to enhance magnon transport in magnetic insulators through the interfacial hybridization effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

The last two decades have seen the emergence of magnonics as a prominent field of research within modern magnetism. One of the main subjects being investigated is the transportation and manipulation of pure spin signals in magnetic insulators, which holds

promise for information technology, as it may enable low-cost and high-speed signal transmission, storage and processing.¹⁻³ To electrically characterize magnon transport in a magnetic insulator, a heavy-metal material is typically employed to convert an electrical signal into a magnon signal inside the insulator and back in the heavy metal via the direct and inverse spin Hall effects (SHE and ISHE, respectively).⁴⁻¹² Several reports have emphasized the influence of the interface between the heavy-metal layer and the magnetic insulator on the magnon transport properties of the latter.¹³⁻¹⁹ Other recent studies on two-dimensional magnetic insulators have shown that magnon behavior is strongly affected by the interfacial exchange coupling between the layers.^{11, 20-22} All these findings suggest that modifying the interface of the magnetic insulator can be an effective approach to enhance the material's magnon transport properties.

Recently, organic semiconductors have drawn attention due to their ability to tune the magnetism of metallic materials via the interfacial hybridization effect, commonly referred to as molecular functionalization.²³⁻²⁶ It has been demonstrated that the interaction between an organic molecular layer and a metal gives rise to a hybrid state within a narrow region of the interface.¹⁷ The interface state can alter the magnetic properties of the metal, the molecular layer, and the system as a whole. Examples include changes in the magnetic anisotropy of a magnetic layer, the spin-polarization of a molecular layer, or the emergence of a magnetic interface at a non-magnetic/organic heterojunction.^{24, 27-30} Given this range of interesting effects brought about by the molecular functionalization of magnetic and non-magnetic metals, it is important to study the hybridization process between organic molecules and a magnetic insulator as a means to enhance magnon transport.

In this work, we demonstrate that the interfacial interactions between the organic molecule CoPc and the magnetic insulator YIG clearly improve its magnon transport properties as compared to those of YIG alone. On the one hand, nonlocal signals from both electrically and thermally excited magnon currents were found to have larger amplitudes in the YIG/CoPc devices as compared to pristine YIG device. On the other hand, we found molecular functionalization modifies the magnetic anisotropy of YIG, as evidenced by the comparison of the field-dependent nonlocal signal of magnon currents and the FMR spectra of YIG/CoPc and YIG films. Finally, the interfacial hybridization was also found to lead to a longer electrically excited magnon diffusion length at low temperature in the YIG/CoPc structure, as confirmed by a lower Gilbert damping constant measured with FMR.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Device fabrication: A 318-nm-thick YIG film (Matesy GmbH), was grown by liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) on a (111) gadolinium gallium garnet ($\text{Gd}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{O}_{12}$, GGG) substrate. The YIG substrate was carefully cleaned with acetone followed by isopropyl alcohol and then dried with a nitrogen gun. The clean sample was loaded into an ultra-high vacuum Magnetron Sputtering system and a 5-nm-thick Pt film was deposited (80 W; 3 mTorr of Ar). Following the deposition process, negative e-beam lithography and Ar^+ -ion milling were used to pattern several $40 \mu\text{m} \times 150 \text{ nm}$ Pt strips to serve as spin injectors and detectors. Finally, electrodes were deposited (5 nm of Ti followed by 45 nm of Au) to contact the Pt strips. Two sets of devices were fabricated on the same YIG substrate, each with Pt injector-detector separations ranging from $1 \mu\text{m}$ to $15 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 1a). One set was covered with a 10-nm-thick film of CoPc, while the other served as

the control. The CoPc layer was deposited via thermal evaporation in ultra-high vacuum.

Device Characterization and FMR Measurement: All measurements were carried out on a Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) by Quantum Design. The electrically and thermally excited magnon currents in the devices were measured in a nonlocal configuration by applying a current at the injector and detecting a voltage at the detectors (Figure 1a), using NF Corporation's LI5660 wide-band digital lock-in amplifier at a frequency of 137 Hz. An external magnetic field was applied in the sample plane, and the relative orientation of the magnetic field and the applied current could be varied by rotating the sample holder. An angle $\theta = 0^\circ$ indicates the direction of the current flow is perpendicular to the external magnetic field, while $\theta = 90^\circ$ indicates it is parallel.

The FMR measurements were based on a coplanar waveguide (CPW) setup. The size of the used YIG sample is 5 mm×5mm and a 10-nm-thick CoPc film is thermally evaporated on half of YIG surface by using a shadow mask. Since the waveguide signal wire has a much smaller width size than the half size of YIG substrate, the YIG and YIG/CoPc regions were separately placed faced down on it to collect the FMR signals from both clean and functionalized YIG surfaces. The input frequency into the waveguide signal wire is fixed from 3 GHz to 12 GHz by using a N5225A Network Analyzer, which is connected to the PPMS system. Finally, by sweeping an in-plane magnetic field, a characteristic resonant spectrum could be obtained.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1a shows a sketch and an optical image of one of our non-local YIG/Pt devices with a 10-nm-thick CoPc overlayer. CoPc is a planar aromatic molecule belonging to the metallo-phthalocyanine (MPc) family. MPcs are composed of four isoindole units connected by azamethine bridges that surround a central metal ion (M^{2+}). The antiferromagnetic properties of CoPc and its potential for creating interfacial hybridization with ferromagnetic metals^{31,32} make this molecule a good candidate to explore the effect of organic overlayers on magnon transport. In our devices, one Pt strip is used as an injector and another, at a distance d , as a detector. A charge current I is sent through the injector, producing a transverse spin current due to the SHE and a spin accumulation at the YIG/Pt interface. When the accumulated spins are antiparallel to the average magnetization of YIG, electrically generated magnons are excited at the interface. At the same time, the temperature gradient produced by the Joule heating generates thermal magnons via the spin Seebeck effect. The electrical and thermal magnon spin currents travel through the YIG and, upon reaching the detector strip, the inverse process of the electrical generation of magnons takes place: the magnons produce a spin accumulation at the YIG/Pt interface, resulting in a spin current that is converted into a charge current in the Pt via the ISHE and detected as a nonlocal voltage signal.³³

The different magnon currents measured in the YIG/CoPc and YIG devices that will be presented in the following discussion could in principle be attributed to different surface qualities of YIG/Pt in the different electrodes instead of the presence of CoPc. To rule this out, we separately measured the angle-dependent spin Hall magnetoresistance (SMR) of several Pt strips with and without CoPc, applying currents and detecting voltages in the same Pt strip. The results, presented in Figure 1b, show the characteristic $\sin^2\theta$ dependence of the SMR.^{4,13,19} Since all the Pt strips were prepared on the same surface with the same geometry, the angle dependent SMR of the different Pt strips can be used to evaluate the impact of the YIG/Pt interface. Figure

1b displays the $\Delta R/R_0$ of a Pt strip with and without the CoPc overlayer, showing identical SMR curves. These results indicate that any differences in the YIG/Pt interfaces due to device fabrication can be considered to have a negligible impact on the magnon signals.

Figure 2a and **2b** exhibits both the electrically (V_{NL}^{el}/I) and thermally (V_{NL}^{th}/I^2) generated nonlocal magnon signals from YIG devices with and without the CoPc layer. The electrically generated magnon signal is derived from the first harmonic of the nonlocal voltage measured at the Pt detector and is expected to follow a $\cos^2 \theta$ dependence due to the $\cos \theta$ dependence of the SHE and ISHE at the injector and detector, respectively.³³ On the other hand, the thermally generated magnon current is obtained from the second harmonic of the nonlocal voltage and is expected to follow a $\cos \theta$ dependence, as in this case only the ISHE at the detector contributes to the angular dependence of the signal. The amplitudes of the nonlocal magnon signals were extracted from the fits shown in Figure 2.^{33, 34, 35} We found that the devices with the CoPc overlayer exhibit larger amplitudes for both the electrically and thermally generated magnon signals. The nonlocal magnon signal is initially generated at the interface of the YIG/Pt injector, propagates along the YIG film, and is converted into a voltage signal at the second interface of YIG/Pt detector by ISHE. Since the CoPc layer is on top of the Pt, it cannot have any influence on the YIG/Pt interface, which is confirmed above by observing the same SMR amplitude with and without the CoPc layer. Therefore, the observed enhancement of the nonlocal signal must be attributed to the YIG/CoPc interface and its effect on the propagation of the magnon. It is reported that CoPc films can show antiferromagnetic (AFM) property with temperature below around 107 K,³¹ so that the magnetic exchange coupling between the ferromagnetic YIG and AFM CoPc molecule is expected. The magnetic property in YIG comes from the Fe atoms so the exchange coupling should originate from the Fe atom and CoPc. When CoPc molecule is adsorbed on Fe surface, a local bonding of CoPc molecular orbitals with Fe 3d bands will induce a strong interfacial hybridization, forming a new hybrid state.³⁶ This hybrid state will change the electronic and magnetic properties of both the molecular side and metal side close to the interfacial region. Particularly, for the Fe atom side, it is explored that the surface π -d hybridization between CoPc and Fe could modify the magnetic exchange interaction and induce a longer magnetic order in Fe.^{37, 38} Based on these findings, the increase observed in the magnon signal may also be explained by the interfacial hybridization of CoPc and YIG (especially its Fe atoms), which can increase the magnon diffusion length and yield larger detected magnon signals. The enhancement of the nonlocal signal is further validated at different applied currents (see Figure S1 in the Supporting Information) and we find that the amplitudes of the nonlocal voltages as a function of the applied current from 100 μ A to 600 μ A show linear and quadratic dependence for electrically and thermally generated magnon currents, respectively, in agreement with previous reports.³³

To confirm the interfacial interaction between the CoPc layer and the YIG film, we first explored the in-plane field-dependent nonlocal magnon current measurements with the external magnetic field perpendicular to the applied current direction in the Pt strips. As previously reported, the hybridization effect between the metal and the molecule can influence the magnetic properties of both the metal and molecular sides.²³⁻³⁰ Therefore, if an interfacial effect between YIG and CoPc exists, differences in the field-dependence of the nonlocal signals should also reflect the modified magnetic properties. We found that the non-local signals for the

electrically generated magnons in the YIG and YIG/CoPc devices show similar saturation trends in the high-field regime (Figure S2 in the Supporting Information) but obvious differences in the low-field regime (Figure 2c). Comparing the field-dependent signals in both devices, we find very different values of the saturation field, which is around 4 Oe in the YIG/Pt device and around 22 Oe in the YIG/Pt with a CoPc overlayer. This change in the magnetic anisotropy in the devices with the CoPc overlayer was also observed at different applied currents and at temperatures up to 140 K (Figure S3 in the Supporting Information). However, this larger magnetic saturation tendency for the YIG/CoPc is much weaker at temperatures over 140 K, indicating that the interfacial effect in YIG/CoPc is temperature dependent. In the case of thermally generated magnon currents, we also observe a larger saturation field of the device covered with the CoPc layer in the low-field region (Figure S4 in the Supporting Information), although it is less pronounced than in the electrically generated case. The modification of the saturation field in both the electrically and thermally generated magnon signals in the YIG/CoPc devices are a clear indication of the interfacial hybridization between YIG and CoPc.

The modified magnetism at the YIG/CoPc interface is further confirmed by FMR, which is a powerful tool to investigate the internal magnetic parameters and spin dynamics of magnetic systems.³⁹⁻⁴³ A comparison of the FMR spectra of the YIG/CoPc and YIG films acquired at 10 K for different excitation frequencies (f) shows clear shifts in the resonant field strength (H_{res}) of the YIG/CoPc film towards lower fields (Figure S5a,b of the Supporting Information), indicating that the interfacial interaction between CoPc and YIG is modifying the magnetic behavior of the system. The H_{res} values of the YIG and YIG/CoPc films are plotted against f in Figures 3a and 3b, along with a fit to the Kittel equation for an in-plane magnetic field⁴⁴

$$f = \frac{\gamma\mu_0}{2\pi} \sqrt{H_{res}(H_{res} + M_{eff})} \quad (1),$$

where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio and M_{eff} stands for the effective saturation magnetization.

This analysis allows us to extract M_{eff} for the system. These same measurements and subsequent analysis were performed as a function of temperature. The extracted M_{eff} values are plotted in Figure 3c in the temperature range 10 K-140 K for the pure YIG and YIG/CoPc films and are found to be consistently larger in the latter, especially at 10 K, where M_{eff} of the functionalized YIG is larger by about 50 Oe. The M_{eff} value obtained from FMR is related to the magnetization property of YIG, affecting by both the saturation magnetization of pure YIG and other surface magnetic interaction. For the YIG single crystal, the saturation magnetization (i.e. M_{eff}) is reported to increase and tend to saturate with reducing temperature (T), that follows well with the typical Bloch's $T^{3/2}$ law.⁴⁵ However, when reducing the film thickness, the saturation magnetization curves of YIG film will be affected by taking into account the geometry, size and surface modification.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ These factors will result in an offset of the saturation magnetization of YIG films in lower temperature region, such as the observed small reduction of M_{eff} for pure YIG film

below 50 K in Figure 3c. Particularly, considering the interfacial hybridization effect between CoPc and YIG, a surface magnetic exchange interaction will contribute an additional magnetic change for the YIG and this interfacial interaction is also temperature dependent. All these parameters will finally result in an increase of M_{eff} at lower temperatures. Together with the larger saturation field observed in the field-dependent measurements (Figure 2c), the larger M_{eff} observed in the YIG/CoPc device serves as further evidence of the hybridization between the CoPc and YIG films and its effect on the interfacial magnetic anisotropy.

A direct confirmation of the impact of the interfacial hybridization between YIG and CoPc on magnon transport can be obtained from the magnon diffusion length (λ_m). To determine λ_m for both electrically and thermally generated magnon currents, we measured the angular dependent nonlocal magnon signal for varying injector-detector separation distances (d). **Figure 4a** and 4b show the amplitude of the electrically generated nonlocal magnon currents as a function of d in the devices without and with a CoPc overlayer, respectively, for different temperatures. Two regimes are clearly visible in the decay curves: in the diffusion regime ($d \ll \lambda_m$), diffusive transport dominates and magnon currents decay algebraically ($\propto 1/d$),^{33, 49-51} whereas in the exponential regime ($d \geq \lambda_m$) magnons travel longer distances and magnon relaxation takes place, as reflected by the characteristic exponential decay ($\propto e^{-d/\lambda_m}$).⁵¹ λ_m can be extracted from a linear fit of the logarithmic nonlocal signals in the exponential regime. Figure 4c plots the obtained λ_m values versus temperature for the YIG/CoPc and YIG devices. The data shows that, below 80 K, λ_m for electrically generated magnons in the YIG/CoPc device can more than double that of the YIG device due to the interfacial effects between YIG and CoPc. The same analysis was made for the thermally generated magnons (Figure S6 in the Supporting Information), but in that case no obvious difference was found in the λ_m of YIG/CoPc and YIG in the measured temperature range. One possible explanation is that the thermal gradient generates magnons in a broad section of the channel, including some quite far from the top interface in which the YIG/CoPc hybridization takes place.⁵⁰ Electrical magnons are more confined to the top surface where they are generated, and hence are more sensitive to the molecular hybridization effects.

It should be noted that the longer λ_m is related to the different damping constants between the YIG/CoPc and YIG structures, which could be verified by FMR measurements. The Gilbert damping constant can be extracted by fitting the linewidth of the FMR spectra (ΔH_0) versus frequency (**Figure 5a**) to the following equation⁵²⁻⁵⁴

$$\mu_0\Delta H = \mu_0\Delta H_0 + \frac{4\pi\alpha_G}{\gamma} f \quad (2)$$

where α_G represents the Gilbert damping, and ΔH_0 is the inhomogeneous linewidth. The fitting result of α for the YIG/CoPc and YIG films at different temperatures is shown in Figure 5b. One can see that the YIG/CoPc structure shows smaller Gilbert damping constants at temperatures below 100 K compared to the YIG film, which is expected to lead to longer magnon diffusion lengths, in agreement with our results.^{49,55} It is noted that the α_G of YIG/CoPc seems temperature independent below temperature of 140 K that is different with the extracted λ_m in Figure 4c. The reason is that λ_m can be affected by some other factors, such as the driven way or magnetic anisotropy field.⁵¹ In YIG/CoPc system, the interfacial effect could change the magnetic property of YIG and it is also obvious temperature dependent. Therefore, both of the changes of α_G values and the temperature-dependent interfacial effect between YIG and CoPc will influence the extracted λ_m at low temperature regions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have investigated the role of the interfacial hybridization between an organic molecule, CoPc, and the magnetic insulator YIG on the magnon transport properties. Our results show this interaction leads to an unambiguous enhancement of the nonlocal signals for both electrically and thermally excited magnon currents. Moreover, field-dependent measurements of nonlocal signals and FMR data reveal that the interfacial hybridization of CoPc and YIG modifies the magnetic anisotropy and lowers the Gilbert damping of the YIG film. As a result, the device with the CoPc overlayer exhibits a longer magnon diffusion length. Our results demonstrate that organic molecules can be used to modulate magnon transport behavior in magnetic insulators thanks to the hybrid interface that forms between both materials.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The supplemental material provides the current dependent nonlocal signals of magnon currents, field-dependent nonlocal voltages of electrically and thermally excited magnon currents, the fitting result of thermally excited magnon diffusion length, and the FMR spectra of YIG/CoPc and YIG films. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: l.hueso@nanogune.eu

Notes: The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Elizabeth Goiri Little for helping in the writing of the manuscript. We acknowledge funding by the Spanish MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF A way of making Europe (Projects No. PID2021-122511OB-I00 and Maria de Maeztu Units of Excellence Programme No. CEX2020-001038-M) and by the European Union H2020 Programme (Projects No. 965046-INTERFAST and No. 964396-SINFONIA). P.Y. acknowledges the Spanish MCIN/AEI and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR for a “Juan de la Cierva” fellowship (grant No. FJ2020-044666-I). W.S. acknowledges grant No. BPN/BKK/2022/1/00010/U/00001 from Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange.

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Figure 1. (a) Sketch of the device (above) and optical image of a typical YIG/Pt device (below). ‘el’ and ‘th’ stand for electrically and thermally excited magnons, respectively, and ∇T is the temperature gradient. The vertical lines in the bottom optical image are four Pt strips (length L) at different injector-detector distances d (1-7 μm in this device), contacted with Ti/Au electrodes. The orange arrow is the applied electric current I and the yellow arrow represents the external magnetic field (B), oriented at an angle θ ($\theta = 0^\circ$ indicates the direction of the current flow is perpendicular to the external magnetic field). (b) Comparison of the angle dependent SMR of a Pt strip in YIG/CoPt and YIG devices, measured at a temperature of 100 K, an applied current of 1 μA , and an external magnetic field of 300 Oe.

Figure 2. Nonlocal voltages of the devices with and without a CoPc overlayer. Voltages are normalized to the applied current in (a) and to the square of the current in (b), representing the electrically and thermally excited cases, respectively. The solid lines are fits to $\cos^2\theta$ in (a) and $\cos\theta$ in (b). Data was collected at 100 K with an applied current of 300 μ A, an applied magnetic field of 300 Oe, and an injector-detector distance of 2 μ m. (c) Field-dependent nonlocal signal of the electrically excited magnon currents in devices with and without a CoPc overlayer in the low-field regime, where the curves of different colors stand for the back (black and blue) and forth (red and green) sweeping direction of the magnetic field. Measurements were taken at 100 K with an applied current of 300 μ A and an injector-detector separation of 2 μ m. The applied magnetic field is perpendicular to the applied current direction in the Pt strip.

Figure 3. (a) (b) FMR frequency as the function of resonant field strength (H_{FMR}) for the YIG (a) and YIG/CoPc (b) films at 10 K. The solid red lines are fits to equation 1 in the main text. (c) Comparison of the extracted effective magnetization M_{eff} versus temperature for YIG/CoPc and YIG films.

Figure 4. Nonlocal voltage amplitude normalized to the applied current as a function of injector-detector distance for the electrically generated magnon current in devices with (a) or without (b) a CoPc overlayer. The red lines are the linear fit in the exponential region from which the magnon diffusion length is extracted. All measurements were performed with an applied current of $100 \mu\text{A}$ and external magnetic field of 300 Oe . (c) Magnon diffusion length as a function of temperature for the electrically generated magnon current in devices with and without a CoPc overlayer.

Figure 5. (a) FMR linewidth of YIG/CoPc and YIG structures as a function of frequency. The black and red dots are the experimental data, and the red solid lines are fits to equation 2 in the main text. (b) Fitted Gilbert damping constants versus temperature for YIG/CoPc and YIG structures.

Supporting Information for

Tuning the magnon transport properties of
 $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ with a cobalt phthalocyanine
molecular layer

*Peisen Yuan¹, Sara Catalano¹, Witold Skowronski^{1,2}, Roger Llopis¹, F òix Casanova^{1,3}
and Luis E Hueso,^{*1,3}*

Figure S1. Nonlocal voltage amplitudes versus applied current for the electrically (a) and thermally (b) excited magnon currents in devices with and without a CoPc overlayer. The devices were operated at 100 K and applied magnetic field of 300 Oe; the injector-detector separation was 2 μm .

Figure S2. Field-dependent nonlocal signal for the electrically excited magnon current for devices with and without the CoPc overlayer in the high applied field regime, where the curves of different colors stand for the back (black and blue) and forth (red and green) sweeping direction of the magnetic field.

Figure S3. Field-dependent nonlocal signals of the electrically excited magnon current for devices with and without a CoPc overlayer at different temperatures (a)-(c) with the same applied current of $200 \mu\text{A}$, and at different applied currents (d) and (f) at the same temperature of 100 K . All the measurements were made with an injector-detector separation of $2 \mu\text{m}$. The curves of different colors stand for the back (black and blue) and forth (red and green) sweeping direction of the magnetic field.

Figure S4. Field-dependent nonlocal signal for the thermally excited magnon current in devices with and without a CoPc overlayer at high applied field regime (a) and low field regime (b). The device was operated at 100 K with an applied current of 300 μ A. The injector-detector separation was 2 μ m. The applied magnetic field was perpendicular to the injected current. The ‘+’ and ‘-’ labels stand for the sweeping magnetic field from negative to positive direction and the opposite direction, respectively.

Figure S5. (a) The measured FMR spectra of YIG/CoPc (red solid lines) and YIG (black dashed lines) structures at different frequencies and $T=10$ K. (b) The FMR spectra of YIG/CoPc and YIG structures at 3 GHz.

Figure S6. Thermally excited nonlocal magnon currents in devices with (a) and without a CoPc overlayer (b) as a function of the injector-detector distance. The red lines are the linear fit in the exponential region from which the magnon diffusion length is extracted. All measurements were made using the same applied current of 0.1 mA and an external magnetic field of 300 Oe. (c) Magnon diffusion length as a function of temperature for the thermally excited magnon currents in devices with and without a CoPc overlayer.